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Animality as Refusal: VALIE EXPORT, Actionism, and Feminist Media Critique

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INTRODUCTION

In the realm of 1960s performance art, VALIE EXPORT stands out as one of the most important and influential figures. She was a pioneer who delivered social critique sharply, sometimes almost confrontationally. EXPORT often shocked people with her performances, mostly in a productive, necessary way – because the shock opened new ways of thinking about the female gendered subject and the systems that shape it.

«In her work, the document as an interface between a fictional «past present» and a later encounter, could be understood as a screen used to mediate history to the future», Mechtild Widrich writes. And indeed, it is tempting to say that VALIE EXPORT became a kind of medium for the future, or even that she significantly shaped the way that future would come to look (Widrich, 2014, p. 53).

Her performative work *Touch Cinema* (1968), is a perfect example (Abb. 1). Radically provocative and courageous for its time, the piece not only offer he possibility of touching the artist's breast inside a wearable «cinema box». It also confronted viewers with urgent questions about sexualisation, the objectification of women, and the role of mass media as one of the most powerful and exploitative cultural machines of the twentieth century (VALIE EXPORT, 2023).

It is important to acknowledge the existence of various feminist and para-artistic groups and formations active in the time of the 1960s–70s, from the Austrian women's movement and the experimental circles of the Vienna Group, to broader European feminist collectives such as Rivolta Femminile, and the emerging networks of feminist performance artists across Europe and the United States.

Widrich reminds us that EXPORT, born Waltraud Höllinger (née Lehner), studied textile design before entering the Viennese art scene in the mid-1960s. She adopted her artist's name as a logo in capital letters in 1967 and even posed with a pack of the Austrian cigarette brand *Smart Export* in order to «legalise» her chosen identity. In the late 1960s, she developed a coherent body of films and performances under the title Expanded Cinema, a concept she elaborated together with Peter Weibel. At that moment, EXPORT was loosely associated with the Viennese Actionists, but by the 1970s, tensions with the group pushed her toward working independently, in a mode she herself called feminist actionism (Feministischer Aktionismus) – a deliberate departure from the machismo of the core Actionist circle (Widrich, 2014, p.53).

There is, however, one significant connection between EXPORT and the Actionists: *the Bildkompendium Wiener Aktionismus und Film* (1970), informally known as the Vienna Book (Wienbuch), which contains the first published description of *Genital Panic*. As the cover

states, the book was edited by Weibel «with the collaboration of» EXPORT – a phrase that, then as now, often masked the undervalued labour of the female co-editor. The volume became the first anthology and could be understood as the baptismal certificate of Viennese Actionism. Weibel and EXPORT defined the Actionists broadly: not only the four central figures of Actionist performance (Günter Brus, Otto Muehl, Rudolf Schwarzkogler, Hermann Nitsch), but also the older concrete poets, collage artists, experimental cabaret performers of the Vienna Group (Wiener Gruppe), the organicist architect Friedensreich Hundertwasser, and the action painter Arnulf Rainer (Widrich, 2014, p. 54).

EXPORT's position in this constellation is therefore not peripheral but structurally vital: she both emerges from and critiques the Actionist milieu, transforming its language into something explicitly feminist, self-aware, and politically charged.

And I also want to name here the work *Bildkompendium* (1970) by Peter Weibel and VALIE EXPORT, a publication that, at least intuitively, feels important to us, even genuinely pivotal. A turning point both in the meaning of becoming a 316-page document of an already forming canon, and in the sense of demonstrating just how far an artist could go – and in EXPORT's case, how much further she was willing to go. It is also a foundational moment because of the very real legal consequences that followed its publication.

What interests us most in this book are the elements one might, for now, simply refer to as the «props», the material residue of Actionist practice: «*The Actionists*» practice involved the use of blood, excrement and other bodily fluids, self-mutilation, sex, orgiastic ritual, and the slaughter of animals – obvious challenges for any editor» (Widrich, 2014. p, 55).

Widrich (2014) argues that, practically speaking, the *Bildkompendium* became a scandal because of the explicitly sexual photographs it contained. These images led to legal action against Weibel and EXPORT. Yet despite, or perhaps because of, this scandal, the publication succeeded in establishing an authoritative historical framework for Actionism, granting it exactly the canon-forming status that its title announces.

Turning back to the issue of the «slaughter of animals», it seems to me that I may have found, if not the original source of inspiration, then at least the conceptual atmosphere of the time – the current of ideas in which all of these practices were simmering. And within this climate, it was EXPORT who used animals in art in a way that feels especially revealing.

In this semester paper, I will focus on the question of how animals appear in the artistic and performance practice of VALIE EXPORT. I will trace how animals enter VALIE EXPORT's performances, not as victims, but as signs, metaphors, and ruptures. I will explore the presuppositions and predispositions that shaped certain artistic decisions, especially those

dealing with representations of pain, suffering, and different forms of harm. Alongside this, I will address the feminist dimensions of EXPORT's work and consider how her approach reframes the visual and symbolic economy of the abuse enacted upon bodies.

It therefore seems both logical and necessary to look more closely at the historical context and examine. The use of animals, and their killing, was central to Viennese Actionism, especially in the work of Hermann Nitsch¹, whose *Orgien Mysterien Theater* involved the ritualised disembowelment of lambs and bulls as part of a Dionysian-Christian fusion of sacrifice and spectacle. Otto Muehl likewise staged performances with animal carcasses, blood and raw meat, pushing the body, both human and non-human, into the territory of abjection and taboo. Even Brus, though less focused on animals, operated within an environment where the theatre of injured bodies, any bodies, was seen as a radical artistic method.

This is not to say that EXPORT participated in the Actionists' sacrificial system. She did not. But what I may have found is the conceptual circulation – the atmosphere of extremity, transgression and corporeal experimentation – in which these practices were the cultural pressure-field. And this is crucial: EXPORT was the only woman in this milieu, navigating and resisting a context where bodies (especially female bodies, but also animal bodies) were treated as sites of violation, rupture, and symbolic annihilation. And EXPORT's relationship to the use of animals in art is less about imitation and more about critical proximity. She stood close enough to Actionism to feel its heat, but far enough to turn its violence outward into critique rather than reenactment.

All of this is extremely interesting and makes a very clever point, and it is astonishing how EXPORT was able to take this theoretical undercurrent of the era – this entire male-oriented approach – and transform it into something far less patriarchal, far less driven by masculine fantasies of transgression. I found a striking formulation in a Master's thesis that articulates the environment she was working in:

«In a decade spanning from 1960 to 1971, four Viennese artists: Otto Muehl, Günter Brus, Hermann Nitsch, and Rudolf Schwarzkogler – executed a prolific number of live actions that caused tremendous public antipathy, authority intervention, imprisonment, and scandal. Their art had strong overtones of taboo-breaking, ritualised dramaturgy, and an array of transgressive performative experiments that aspired to self-liberation from the conventional

¹ The work of Nitsch, Muehl, Schwarzkogler and Brus is not only historically significant but also profoundly controversial. Their performances involved a level of violence and corporeal exposure that raises real ethical questions, which is why I have deliberately decided not to include photographic documentation of these actions in our paper.

*confines imposed by society. It was conceived as a brutal reaction against the dominant ideology of Catholicism, right-wing social conservatism, bourgeois convention, and the sublimated postwar social climate of Austria. This thesis scrutinises the history of misconceptions associated with Actionism and focuses its analysis on the intentions of the artists and their engagement with avant-garde art at the time*².

«Daniele Roussel argues that to understand Actionism, you must look at Austrian psychology after WWII – not just art history».

(Seserko-Ostrogonac, 2010, pp. 5,9)

What becomes clear, especially when reading this, is just how radically EXPORT redirected and reconfigured this energy. The same cultural pressure cooker produced two very different trajectories: the Actionists' violent and often hyper-masculine confrontations, and EXPORT's fiercely intelligent feminist counter-movement, which used similar strategies of exposure and embodiment but refused the machismo that defined the original group. EXPORT rejects sacrificial logic because it depends on a passive victim, a violated living form, and a patriarchal drama of transgressive power. Her feminism transforms the same climate of violence into a critique of subjugation, replacing the sacrificed physical subject with an active, self-determining subject who confronts the viewer rather than submitting to them. Because EXPORT replaces sacrifice with relationality and interactivity.

² Viennese Actionism did not emanate out of aesthetic experimentation alone. It was a deliberate, violent rejection of the main ideological forces that shaped post-war Austrian society. Nitsch's sacrificial rituals, Muehl's chaotic orgies, Bruss's self-mutilation... all of this can be understood as bringing repressed ideology to the surface, in the only language Austria seemed to understand: the language of the body set aside for annihilation.

In postwar Austria, society sublimated the trauma and guilt of Nazi collaboration, the Holocaust, fascist ideology, and wartime atrocities. People did not openly confront what happened. They repressed it, pretending Austria was a «victim». Actionism saw this repression as poisonous and responded by bringing hidden violence to the surface, reenacting collective trauma, exposing what society wanted to forget, and refusing the silent clean-up of fascism.

Part I: Actionism, Confrontation, and Its Discontents

1.1 Actionism and the Economy of Shock

Actionism is both closure and genesis.

Widrich writes: «*For Weibel and EXPORT as the editors of the Wienbuch, the confrontation was a necessary addition to the action...*» (Widrich, 2014, p. 60).

The canonisation of Actionism relied heavily on confrontation as both method and outcome, producing a mediated image of political insurgency that risks conflating scandal with resistance.

I have something very contemporary and very uncomfortable here:

a bad commercial is also a commercial

bad fame is also fame

questionable works resonate

scandal reaches ears and eyes

Actionism understood, very early, that shock travels faster than nuance and that confrontation guarantee circulation. In Fact, his is not naive rebellion, it is strategic antagonism.

And Widrich's point up here is that the Wienbuch didn't just document actions, it canonised scandal itself.

Actionism was retrospectively framed as a form of political resistance: images of police cordons, arrests, and provocations were read as evidence of anti-fascist struggle, insurgency, and opposition to a police state. Yet this framing is deeply mediated, constructed after the fact, and partly mythological. Confrontation was undoubtedly necessary to break the silence, but confrontation also carries risks. It can be commodified, absorbed into national mythology, emptied of content, and reframed seamlessly in a media organising principle. Actionism operated dangerously close to this threshold, where scandal begins to substitute for politics and visibility for agency.

EXPORT stepped back from it, not because she was less radical, but because she was more precise. She realised that not every shock is critical, not every scandal is resistance, not every image of repression equals politics. Anticipating these dangers, she developed works that actively resist heroic narrativization.

Critics have called the Actionists many things, but the term I find very telling is «*troubled*». It sounds almost «witty», so «witty», in fact, that we almost forget that one of the movement's founding figures went to prison for the sexual abuse of minors (girls), it was Otto Muehl. One

almost forgets, but this is not something that can ever truly be forgotten. And at this point, it feels necessary to give the critics, even the haters, a chance to speak for themselves:

Micchelli (2014) notes that «*The four artists who made up the core of the movement – Günter Brus, Otto Muehl, Hermann Nitsch and Rudolf Schwarzkogler – witnessed the ravages of World War II and its aftermath, though only one of them, Muehl, was old enough to fight, entering the Wehrmacht in 1943 at the age of 18*», and «*After the passage of fifty years, the questions it (Vienna Actionism) raised about the limits and origins of art remain no less troubling or closer to resolution*».

There is something almost circular in this discourse: men criticising men who criticised other men and the world order, a closed loop of masculine confrontation. The same article goes on to note that «*Their performances – Nitsch's in particular, which involved slaughtered animals, viscera and crucifixions – evoked Dionysian rites...*» before making a striking leap, linking Actionism to Wagnerian ideas of the *Gesamtkunstwerk* and, by extension, to the cultural imaginaries historically associated with Nazism (Micchelli, 2014).

The comparison is provocative... Actionists are effectively named as Nazis more than once, and Wagner is invoked as a haunting shadow. Yet what remains underdeveloped in this account is what matters most here: the sustained exploitation of animal bodies and the parallel objectification of women. These forms of violence are acknowledged, but not fully unpacked. The article leans heavily on ideological genealogy and symbolic association, but the material realities of animal suffering and gendered domination receive comparatively less attention.

This imbalance suggests how easily discussions of extremity can drift toward grand historical metaphors, Nazism, Wagner, and total art. While leaving the violence itself becomes almost abstract.

The issue that Actionists raised, the role of animal bodies in radical art, has repeatedly intersected with animal rights activism in later decades, showing that the concerns Actionism provoked are not confined to art history but resonate in broader ethical debates.

Binnie (2019) states that his thesis examines the ethical problems inherent in the use of nonhuman species within certain areas of contemporary art practice. Drawing on humanist faith in «reason», articulated by feminist theorists such as Josephine Donovan and Carol J. Adams, which are foundational to the development of any research, particularly through the lens of an ecofeminist ethic of care.

Binnie further argues that the appearance of nonhuman animal bodies as material constituents of artworks throughout the twentieth century raises urgent ethical questions, especially where killing and violence are involved. As performance practices emerged through radical

movements such as Dada, Futurism, and later Vienna Actionism, artists increasingly moved away from representation toward the literal use of animal bodies. Yet in these works, the animal rarely appears as an end in itself. Instead, nonhuman bodies function as expressive instruments for human concerns like religion, trauma, nationalism, masculinity and death. Hermann Nitsch's disembowelling of a lamb in *The Orgies Mysteries Theatre* (1962), Joseph Beuys' whispered monologue to a dead hare in *How to Explain Pictures to a Dead Hare* (1965), Jannis Kounellis' tethering of twelve live horses inside a gallery space (1969), and Kim Jones' burning of live rats in *Rat Piece* (1976) differ formally, but they share a common structure: nonhuman animals are positioned as symbolic carriers for human meaning, their bodies subordinated to artistic intent (Binnie, 2019, p.17).

Kieran Cashell describes transgressive art as a practice that deliberately seeks to unsettle its audience, not accidentally but by design, through what he calls an uncompromising interrogation of conservative moral frameworks (Binnie, 2019, p.79). He goes further, defining aesthetic transgression as «any act of violation presented under the alibi of art» (Cashell, 2009, p.1), a formulation that is almost uncannily precise when applied to Vienna Actionism.

The comparison frequently drawn between figures such as Marina Abramović or Bob Flanagan and Hermann Nitsch begins to fracture here: self-inflicted risk, however extreme, operates within a different ethical juncture than the instrumentalisation of bodies that cannot consent. When nonhuman animals are incorporated into transgressive performance, the claim to «meta-ethical validity» risks functioning less as philosophical justification than as moral exemption. (Cashell, 2009; Binnie, 2019, p. 79).

This again signals a failure to recognise nonhuman animals as relational beings and instead reinscribes them within what Rosi Braidotti has described as a necro-political economy, one in which life and death are rendered usable, exchangeable, and ultimately disposable (Binnie, 2019, p 40).

Actionist aesthetics did not disappear with the end of the movement; they continue to provoke ethical controversy. The critical reaction to Hermann Nitsch's participation in *Dark Mofo* (2017) shows that the use of animal bodies in art remains contested territory, one that animal rights groups interpret not as ritual but as exploitation (Australian Broadcasting Corporation, 2017).

Actionism splintered³ around 1967–1970, while its performances were splinters in the public eye.

³ Widrich, 2014.

Actionism became a long-term flashpoint in cultural debates about animal cruelty allegations. Were Actionists arrested⁴ specifically for killing animals?

Short answer: Not directly, but animal slaughter was absolutely part of what triggered state intervention.

What emerges is a familiar pattern: a system that excuses male excess, discovers its moral vigilance when a woman intervenes in the economy of repression. And now one can better see why parts of the cultural press seemed almost eager to scrutinise EXPORT with constant suspicion. It follows a familiar cultural script: male transgression is intellectualised, but when a woman challenges the architecture of repression itself, she becomes the one marked for correction.

EXPORT is a historically documented example of the gendered policing of women artists, especially when they work with themes aligned with violence, ritual, or body politics. She is the one who ended up in court facing accusations of animal cruelty allegations, despite the fact that no animal had been harmed. The press attempted to pin on her the same accusations they rarely applied to the male Actionists.

I will continue this line of investigation in the next chapter.

⁴ Almost all core members of Viennese Actionism faced arrests, legal sanctions, or imprisonment. After the infamous Art and Revolution event at the University of Vienna (1968), Brus was sentenced to 6 months in prison for «degrading the symbols of the state» and public indecency. But Brus escaped to West Berlin in 1969 to avoid imprisonment. Hermann Nitsch was arrested several times in the 1960s, charged with «gross public indecency» for performances involving naked bodies, blood, and slaughtered animals (Sheik, 2020, p.23). In some cases, live slaughter occurred, but was legally performed by licensed butchers and supervised by veterinarians, as documented by the Nitsch Foundation and Kunsthalle Bremen. Otto Muehl's history must be separated into two parts: his art-related arrest in 1968 (one month in prison for public indecency during *Art and Revolution*) and his later, unrelated 1991 conviction for sexual abuse of minors and other offences (Online Archive of California, n.d; Museums Quartier Wien, 2010-2011). Oswald Wiener, too, was arrested after *Art and Revolution*, though he was ultimately acquitted (Wiener Aktionismus Museum, n.d.).

1.2 Actionism's Limits: Toward a Feminist Reconfiguration

In the collaborative work *VALIE EXPORT / Peter Weibel* (1968), the divergence between EXPORT's approach and that of Viennese Actionism becomes clear. As the Archives of Women Artists, Research and Exhibitions (n.d.) points out, two critical differences distinguish EXPORT from her Viennese Actionist contemporaries: she refused spectacular violence, and she experimented with various media to construct identity through socially disseminated language and ritual.

Aus der Mappe der Hundigkeit / From the Portfolio of Dogness (1968) a charming performative call-out, in a subtle contrast to Actionist uses of animals and the abuse of animal bodies (Abb. 2). A great deal has already been written about this work, and I want to write about it once more, because it has left an irreversible mark and remains an inexhaustible source of inspiration for later generations. Thanks to art, and thanks to the photo camera, we are left with five black-and-white photographs documenting the performance. Suddenly, Vienna's Kärntner Straße becomes the witness to one of the most significant and legendary images of its time.

Rather than sacrificing an animal body, this work stages animality itself as a social position imposed on a human subject. She also rearranges positions of power within the human–animal world: the man–human–animal occupies a position of strength, a vulnerable form, that is physically capable and able to defend itself, unlike enslaved animals subjected to asymmetrical power relations.

Yet the performance traces something else: the oppressor is always also an oppressor in multiple dimensions. Domination operates as a spectrum, extending into reproductive and symbolic forms of violence. EXPORT herself appears wearing a fur coat and, as Heinrich (2023) notes, «*Clad in a fur coat and heeled leather loafers, VALIE EXPORT might be the epitome of the Austrian post-war bourgeoisie – shaped by Catholicism and conservatism – were it not for the young man, artist Peter Weibel, that she leads on a leash like a dog.*» (Heinrich, 2023).

The reference to the bourgeoisie cuts deeper than it first appears. Class enters almost silently, not declared, but assumed, operating as a background condition that rarely needs to name itself. It is precisely this invisibility that gives it power. In late-1960s Austria and Germany, fox fur was a very common bourgeois status symbol, cheaper than mink but still signalling class aspiration (true to say: fox, rabbit, mink, it hardly mattered which animal). I couldn't find any written source that specifies the coat in *From the Portfolio of Dogness* (1968) as fox fur. All

the reliable texts only say «fur coat», nothing about the animal and perhaps that ambiguity is the point. Whether fox or rabbit, whether deer skin pulled over human legs, the animal reduced to material, all of these raise an uncomfortable question: who owns whom, and under what internal economy? What is the class position of the animal once it becomes a garment, symbol, or surface? And what does it mean that this transformation reads as normal, even elegant?

Here, class is not an external theme but a latent structure. It binds together hegemonic force over animals, over bodies, and over women through systems of possession and display. The bourgeois image does not collapse under critique; it absorbs it. The coat remains luxurious even as it marks visible violence. This is the harsh truth the work refuses to soften: exploitation does not always announce itself as brutality. More often, it appears polished, wearable, and socially acceptable. Art confronts us with this contradiction, but it does not resolve it. And perhaps it cannot. The narrative resists coherence because power itself operates through fragmentation – through habits so deeply internalised that they no longer appear ideological at all.

EXPORT does not offer a way out of this structure. She places us inside it. And what turn out to be visible is not a moral hierarchy, but a system that continues to function precisely because it feels self-evident. We don't want to oversimplify here – we should always acknowledge the playful, carnivalesque aspect that EXPORT uses to mix power and comedy, rather than simply reverse the roles.

And the moral here, not in a biblical sense, but in an almost universal one. Humanity's obsessive urge to anthropomorphise animals often conceals its own ignorance and decay. The desire for self-aggrandisement, a fundamental disease of both humanity and patriarchy, diagnoses itself as a machine of universal exploitation. By leading Peter Weibel through the streets of Vienna on a leash, EXPORT lays bare the mechanisms through which bodies are disciplined, animalised, and rendered obedient. The violence at work is not physical, but structural: a violence of hierarchy, gender, and species.

Shown at the 2024 exhibition in Berlin⁵, the photograph was displayed in the same room as *I (Beat It)*⁶ and its related works (Abb. 3). The image *Man on a Leash* (Abb. 2) remains

⁵ *Valie Export: Retrospective* was presented at C/O Berlin from 27 January to 22 May 2024. Bringing together early *Expanded Cinema* actions, symbolic performances, urban interventions, and experimental photography. Curatorial framing, the exhibition highlighted how EXPORT's work consistently challenges the marginalisation of women within patriarchal structures while expanding the language of performance into the fields of media and visual culture (Valie Export: Retrospective, 2024).

⁶ The performances *I (Beat It) from 1978 and II (1980)*: Installation, video installation. In 2024, *Retrospective* it ludes monitors, videotapes, a photo of Valie Export with lead bands around her wrists and ankles and used motor oil.

unmistakably «in-your-face», strong but not too strong, with a smile of «shyness» and maybe satisfaction. Even today, it raises a recurring question: how was it possible for a female artist to produce something so unapologetically bold, so direct, and so lucid?

But in *I (Beat It)*, the barking of dogs mirrors the aggressive and defensive posture women are forced to adopt in order to endure constant pressure (Abb. 3). The bound female figure lies in a sticky, muddy liquid, where suffocating in silence is the best, she can hope for. Meanwhile, the relentless, grating barking continues, irritating and unintelligible. It is devoid of any self-reflection and serves only to perpetuate the idea of senseless and ongoing oppression. It is interesting to see the description of publication of this triangular setup from 1978 year: «*the dogs' barking acts as a symbol – a constant, aggressive call from the Father State, Mother Nature, and male ideology. The triangle of monitors also represents a chain of «trinities», ranging from the sacred – Father, Son, and Holy Spirit – to the profane – human, gender, and morality*» (Export & Faber, 1997, p.138).

The figure of the dog continues to function as a loaded symbol. Submission, loyalty, obedience – these are not neutral traits, but learned behaviours produced through domestication. And this is where EXPORT's critique sharpens. The historical domestication of dogs mirrors the ways in which women have been expected to behave: tamed, compliant, manageable. In EXPORT's work, animals do not merely stand in for women; they reflect a shared position within systems of hierarchy. Both are marginalised, disciplined, and spoken for. Within this cultural mode of thinking, women are aligned with animals – not as subjects, but as beings to be controlled.

We want to look more closely at these events, particularly through the role animals play within this space. The situation becomes especially strange in later versions of the installation, where a printed silhouette of a bound woman lies on an oil-slicked floor. The scene feels ritualistic, almost liturgical, recalling the Catholic Mass and carrying a dark, nearly magical charge. It even faintly echoes the aesthetics of Marina Abramovic.

Yet when attention shifts to the dogs, the German shepherds confined in boxes, it becomes clear that they are not free either. Locked inside black cubes, they are unable to move or act. Barking is all that remains to them: a voice without agency. The human condition is mirrored here. Similarly, as the woman on the floor is bound and silenced, the dogs are trapped, reduced to sound, a raw form of expression that is present but rarely acknowledged.

If barking is read as a nonverbal protest, a gesture of frustration, or a demand for recognition, it begins to resonate with the experiences of women struggling to break free from forms of captivity that persist today. In this sense, the dogs take on a ritualistic role, as witnesses,

guardians, or unwilling participants in a performance that exposes how bodies are controlled, particularly female bodies, within religious and patriarchal systems.

The dogs are actively managed, and in this management, they echo the internal logic of the work itself: a closed loop of mediation and control. Just as animals are subjected to systems of discipline, so too are humans shaped by repetitive structures that regulate behaviour and perception.

Barking, often dismissed as a nonfunctional or meaningless act, can signal distress, resistance, or the marking of a boundary. Yet through repetition and lack of response, it risks becoming emptied of effect – noise without consequence. Dogs can be trained, disciplined, or neglected into silence. In this, they mirror human subjects who continue to reproduce oppressive patriarchal patterns, either because these structures remain invisible or because breaking them would mean relinquishing the security they provide.

This style is decisive. Where Actionism relied on real harm to provoke confrontation, EXPORT produces discomfort without reproducing cruelty. The animal does not appear as a victim, but as a metaphor through which structural inequality becomes visible. At this register, *Hundigkeit* transforms the question of animal violence into a feminist critique of power, replacing sacrificial brutality with symbolic exposure. EXPORT does not romanticise this analogy. She exposes it. By staging these relationships in public space and fixing them through the photographic image, she forces the viewer to confront how deeply such hierarchies are embedded, and how easily they are naturalised. What looks playful is, in fact, structural. And what appears symbolic cuts into the real organisation of power.

Although Viennese Actionism was a post-war avant-garde phenomenon rooted in ritualised transgression and shock, its legacy has continued to surface in ongoing controversies over animal use in art long after the movement's original 1960s context. The issue that Actionists raised, the role of animal bodies in radical art, has repeatedly intersected with animal rights activism in later decades, showing that the concerns Actionism provoked are not confined to art history but resonate in broader ethical debates.

1.3 Animals as Mediators: Ritual, Trauma, and Refusal

VALIE EXPORT and the «Vogel» Misunderstanding: A Gendered Case Study

Approaching the conceptual core of this work, I want to pose a question about killings. Were there killings? Perhaps there were, and will be, in the kitchen of any non-vegan housewife; killings (not only in its literal sense⁷) also occur through the erasure of subjectivity within the family, within state systems, and within religious orders. And for EXPORT, these killings matter...

VALIE EXPORT never «killed that Vogel». The accusation that she suffocated live birds with wax emerged from a spectacular misunderstanding, and an equally spectacular readiness to believe it. The work in question, *Asemie - The Inability to Express Oneself Through Facial Expression / Asemie – die Unfähigkeit, sich durch Mienenspiel ausdrücken zu können* (1973), is a conceptual film concerned with the limits of human expression (Abb. 4). The bird appears only as an image: a stand-in, a visual mediator within a critique of social conditioning. No animal was physically present, and none was harmed.

The controversy began in 1977, when an explanatory leaflet for the exhibition *Körpersplitter* (Nächst St. Stephan, Vienna) listed «live bird» among the materials (EXPORT, n.d.). This brief and poorly worded phrase was enough to ignite a tabloid scandal. The *Kronen Zeitung*⁸ reported that EXPORT had poured hot wax over several birds until they suffocated. The allegation rapidly escalated into a formal charge of animal cruelty allegations.

EXPORT was forced to defend herself in court. There, she demonstrated through the logic of montage, editing, and filmic illusion that the work involved no living animal. The accusation collapsed under scrutiny. She was acquitted, and the legal documents remain preserved in her archive.

What I see here is not only the factual error, but the speed and confidence with which violence was attributed to EXPORT. The assumption that a female artist working with animal imagery must also be capable of cruelty reveals a deeper pattern: a readiness to conflate representation with action, symbolism with harm, and conceptual mediation with bodily violence, a conflation

⁷ I use the term «killings» here, not only in its literal sense, but to name processes of erasure, dispossession, and symbolic annihilation.

⁸ In 1977, an explanatory leaflet for the exhibition *Körpersplitter* (Galerie nächst St. Stephan, Vienna) listed «lebender Vogel» («live bird») as material. Following a report in the *Kronen Zeitung*, which falsely claimed that EXPORT had suffocated live birds with hot wax, she was charged with animal cruelty. EXPORT successfully demonstrated that the effect resulted from montage and editing techniques. She was acquitted; the court documents are preserved in the artist's archive.

far less readily applied to her male contemporaries. Seen this way, the «Vogel» scandal exposes less about EXPORT's practice than about the gendered expectations projected onto it.

VALIE EXPORT consistently sought to dismantle the boundaries that constrain human beings. What matters, however, is that limits interested her not as prohibitions, but as tools, something to be redirected, misused, and repurposed. Her work repeatedly tests thresholds: of the body, of language, of space, and of visibility itself.

One of her conscious refusals was the visual regime of domestic filmmaking prevalent at the time, the seemingly innocent, private, and sentimental imagery that masked underlying structures of control. EXPORT rejects this «safe» visuality and instead places the body, particularly the female body, on the front line.

She exposes male voyeurism by positioning herself within it. Through her videos and her use of animals, she does not stage-controlled provocation for its own sake, but reveals how humans relate to animals, often indirectly, filtered through surreal displacement rather than literal confrontation. Animals appear not as decorative elements, but as figures through which social relations are made visible.

Marina Abramović recounts in an interview for the film «*Valie Export - Ikone und Rebellin 2025*» (00:08:00) how deeply she was influenced by EXPORT, even repeating Genital Panic performances⁹ (Abb. 5). Yet what Abramović recognised in EXPORT was not an aesthetics of pure provocation. EXPORT's work was never about exposure alone; it was about precision, positioning, and exposure.

At this point, I shift the argument from reception to genealogy.

From *Ikone und Rebellin* (2025), it becomes clear that Vienna remained the central city of EXPORT's artistic life, the place that received her as an artist and continuously charged her work with meaning, especially her photographic practice and her engagement with the body in relation to time, language, and space. At the same time, her native city of Linz occupies an important position in her formation. Linz was marked by a strong Catholic presence. EXPORT attended a church-run school, taught by nuns, and experienced the bombing of the city during her childhood. This Catholic background does not disappear; it stays with her as a kind of *bruised thought*, something she both carries and resists. The material suggests that this background became a site of denial and, at the same time, a space of liberation from the confused morality of authority. A very Nietzschean moment.

⁹ Abramovic's re-enactment of Valie Export's Genital Panic (1969).

In November 2005, Marina Abramović performed a variation of VALIE EXPORT's work as part of her project *Seven Easy Pieces* at the Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum in New York.

I am not the first scholar to notice this parallel; some have written about it already, invoking a shared language of radicality, body-centred thinking, and negation. A particularly productive articulation appears in Gaëlle Périot-Bled's analysis, which draws on Nietzsche's figure of Baubô in the preface to *The Gay Science* (*Die fröhliche Wissenschaft*; sometimes translated as *The Joyful Wisdom* or *The Joyous Science*) to confront a perspectivist understanding of truth with contemporary practices of simulacrum in the work of VALIE EXPORT. Here, the body is not revealed as truth, but mobilised as a strategic site where representation is destabilised rather than affirmed (Périot-Bled, 2023).

But what occurs unavoidable to me is something more specific: Nietzsche himself was the son of a pastor. And precisely from this position, he writes *The Antichrist*, turns toward Dionysus, toward occult poetry, toward philosophy with a hammer. He breaks old standards violently, and yet he is also cruel to the body as such. The human is merely a bridge toward something beyond itself. And from this logic, almost automatically, Chuck Palahniuk appears, with his idea of «self-improvement through self-destruction».

For EXPORT, liberation from convent discipline and religious order was not abstract; it was deeply personal. When one grows up in an environment where God is consistently framed as male, discomfort becomes almost inevitable, rebellion a logical response. Such an upbringing often produces what could be described as a form of Christian trauma, and EXPORT repeatedly returns to this wound. From it emerges a ritualistic sensibility that runs through her work.

Since direct articles about EXPORT and Nietzsche are rare, and so little has been written about EXPORT and Chuck Palahniuk¹⁰.

Palahniuk's protagonists in *Fight Club*¹¹, for example, attempt to escape a closed system, the world as it is given, structured and suffocating. But there is no real exit. By destroying one system, the hero simply constructs another. Palahniuk is often called a «modern Kurt Vonnegut», his work linked to confessional writing, to autobiography, to the *novel of creation*. He becomes one of the cult authors of the generation of loners, producing a text that proved foundational for contemporary mass culture. Those who read him in the 1990s carried his ideas into the world: a redefinition of success, goals, masculinity and freedom. They broke rules,

¹⁰ VALIE EXPORT and Chuck Palahniuk are two distinct figures from different artistic fields (performance art/film and literature, respectively).

¹¹ *Fight Club*, Chuck Palahniuk's 1996 novel, operates as a satire of toxic masculinity, exposing it while simultaneously seducing the reader with its violence and rhetoric. Palahniuk is not introduced here as a direct influence, but as a cultural symptom of the same post-Christian, post-heroic logic that EXPORT interrogates through the body.

believing Tyler Durden's words: «*Maybe self-improvement isn't the answer. Maybe self-destruction is*» (Palahniuk, 1996).

And then there is that passage, that almost embarrassingly good in how clearly it articulates the nihilistic drive we are circling here: a generational depression without war, without catastrophe, without an external enemy. Therefore, war must be declared inwardly: spiritually, culturally, existentially. A revolution against culture itself. A profoundly masculine manifesto, yes, but one that belongs to this lineage of anti-heroic nihilism, explicitly Nietzschean in its logic of deconstruction toward reconstruction.

But not deconstruction alone, deconstruction as a movement toward reconstruction, a process that is spiritually central to EXPORT's work.

For us, what's especially important is the EXPORT's 1972 manifesto, written for an exhibition with only female artists. In it, the artist encourages women to participate in creating a new reality within the media. With revolutionary fervour, she speaks of resistance and the fight for social equality, self-determination, and women's self-awareness – for a culture free from male domination in all areas of life, including art. I believe she captures the spirit of her art in this manifesto – a self-aggressive spirit or self-exposing radicalism evident in its rawness, honesty, and self-exposure.

Peter Assmann commented on the installation *Obsessive Idea*: «...this aggressive act of social dominance is expressed in an aggressive way, as aggression directed against both one's own body and one's surroundings» (Export & Faber, 1997, p. 206).

This is where EXPORT becomes interesting again.

Her work does not aim at transcendence beyond the body. It does not abandon the body as a bridge to something «higher». Instead, it insists on the body as a site of conflict, repetition, and ritual. This ritual dimension of deconstruction becomes especially visible in works involving animals, where repetition, cyclicity, and symbolic gesture recur. Animals function not as sacrifices, but as mediators, figures suspended between worlds, between myth and conflict, between silence and address.

In *Ikone und Rebellin*, Alfred Kubin is mentioned as an important influence, an artist whose work fascinated EXPORT but also frightened her. This tension between attraction and fear matters. It marks the unstable territory she inhabits: a space where images are powerful, symbolism is dangerous, and mediation must be handled carefully.

And so, the ritual of church trauma shifts into a domestic or kitchen ritual, one that women, in particular, perform in a voluntary – compulsory way within a patriarchal order. In *Unsichtbare Gegner / Invisible Adversaries* (1976), all the elements of a small ritual are

present (Abb. 6). There are visible «sacrifices»: a fish, a turtle, a mouse, a parrot and a beetle. With the exception of the fish, none of these animals is actually cut up or eaten; they are replaced by substitutes – a bread roll, an apple, a pear. The rhinoceros beetle, however, does suffer, though, as far as I know, it was not eaten.

We see cheese shaped like a hand, and a child lying in a refrigerator, a place where, clearly, a baby does not belong. Yet the provocation here is not simply about shock. It carries a distinctly Christian charge. In the act of communion, believers consume the body of Christ and drink his blood. Here, the infant becomes an echo of ritual sacrifice, in line with the fish, a long-standing symbol of Christ, reinforces this reference. The gesture is highly conceptual, but also disturbingly intimate.

Then there are the sacrificial tools: the blood-stained knife, an object that becomes a symbol of domestic labour, particularly of the housewife of that era. EXPORT once told Abramović: «If I have to cause myself pain, and if this pain is capable of freeing me from the fear of pain, then pain is normal – and acceptable» (*Ikone und Rebellin*, 2025, 32:59). One does not have to search far to recall Christian martyrs, or Christ himself, who is said to have liberated humanity through suffering. I am not suggesting that EXPORT imagined herself as Christ or as a sacrificial lamb. But martyrdom parallels are undeniably present, and they are worth thinking through, especially when considered alongside Abramović's later work.

In «*Ikone und Rebellin 2025*», EXPORT mentions Carolee Schneemann's *Eye Body* (1963), along with Yvonne Rainer and Yoko Ono, as important points of reference. These names situate her practice within a network of women artists who used their bodies not as symbols to be consumed, but as sites of resistance, exposure, and redefinition.

Part II: From Sacrifice to Sign: Feminist Reconfigurations of Animality

2.1 Animal Voices, Symbolism, and Religious Residue

I want to inspect another work by EXPORT, which is titled *«man & woman & animal»* and seems suitable for my analysis (Abb. 7). Here, the descriptive moment is crucial, since the animal itself does not appear in the frame. Instead, what one sees is: a woman masturbates with the stream of a shower in a bathtub; a vagina with blood; a vagina with semen; onto a photograph of a menstruating vagina, blood drips from a man's hand and mixes with the developing fluid. Together with the sounds that go with these images, this makes up the entire film's action.

I came across a remarkable 1976 interview with VALIE EXPORT conducted by Helke Sander, which contains a wealth of first-hand information and statements from the artist. For this reason, it is worth examining this material more closely.

VALIE EXPORT speaks about fear and guilt, as well as about bothering sexuality, and masturbation in particular, as a formative process, especially for young girls. In a world structured and governed by men, it is also men who regulate female sexuality: its visibility, its fluids, its orgasms, and the conditions under which they may appear. Sexuality is not lived, but administered.

Sander remarks: «I felt that the film often repelled women, and men as well» (EXPORT & Sander, 1976, p. 39). EXPORT noted the discomfort and linked it to the absence of the head and the invisibility of facial expression. Viewers felt unsettled because they could not read, decode, or reassure themselves through the face and its emotion.

Yet for EXPORT, this withdrawal was not a loss but a strategy. The missing head does not signal dehumanisation; it marks the emergence of animality. By removing the face, the primary site of social legibility and moral interpretation, EXPORT redirects attention to bodily movement, rhythm, and repetition. The body ceases to function as an expressive surface for emotion and instead operates as a physical process.

In this sense, animality appears not as regression, but as resistance. It disrupts the demand that female sexuality be readable, narratable, and contained. Interrupting the head refuses identification, empathy, and voyeuristic reassurance, allowing the body to exist outside the frameworks of shame, confession, and moral surveillance. Animality here names a mode of being that precedes and exceeds the symbolic order imposed upon female sexuality.

EXPORT articulates this like: «I believe that these cropped movements of the body are important, for example, how the thighs sometimes clap together, which I like very much

because it is so animalistic. Every time I see the film, it reminds me of fish, which is why the title is «man & woman & animal». It says that what connects man and woman, among many other things, is nature» (EXPORT & Sander, 1976, p. 39).

Animality is not introduced visually, but kinaesthetically and sonically. The body moves without a face, without expression, without confession. Sound takes over where representation withdraws. EXPORT's choice of dolphins in the final sound segment is therefore unlikely to be accidental. Dolphins are culturally coded as engaging in complex, often aggressive and non-reproductive sexual behaviours, forms of pleasure detached from romanticised human intimacy. EXPORT herself notes that she would have preferred to use recordings of turtles during mating, had they been available. In both cases, animal sexuality appears not as innocence, but as intensity, repetition, and excess.

This sonic progression, from her own voice to a human–male–animalistic roar and finally to dolphins, stages a gradual displacement of the human voice as a stable site of meaning. Language dissolves into sound; sound slips into animality. What emerges is not a metaphor for nature, but a challenge to the moral and symbolic regulation of sexuality.

This becomes especially clear in the discussion of shame. When Helke Sander asks whether it was difficult to overcome shame, reminding us that women are raised to keep their legs closed, EXPORT's answer is unexpectedly precise (EXPORT & Sander, 1976). She acknowledges shame as a concept, but refuses it in relation to her body. Pressed further, she names her Catholic upbringing and, with devastating clarity, recounts early sexual violence. Yet even here, the film does not operate as a confession. It does not ask for empathy or absolution.

Instead, man & woman & animal displaces Catholic shame by refusing the visual and narrative codes through which sexuality is usually moralised. The film does not merely show a sexual organ; it shows it burdened with symbols: menstruation, semen, blood, development and sound. This symbolic density is precisely what renders the work incompatible with television and state-controlled media. As EXPORT notes, socially produced pornography persists as long as sexuality and its expression remain regulated by institutional authority. Animality here is not a return to nature, but a refusal of moral capture.

All in all, I have some critical angles here – animality plays a central conceptual role in film, but animals themselves remain placed out of context, sexualised and abstracted. They function less as agents than as symbolic surfaces onto which human anxieties about sexuality, control, and repression are projected. In this sense, animality risks becoming a metaphor rather than an encounter. They function here as a refusal of shame and symbolic regulation, but themselves

remain abstracted. By displacing animals into the realm of symbolism, EXPORT avoids literal violence, but this displacement also sidesteps the ethical complexity of interspecies relations. Animality becomes a concept rather than a relationship or dialog. While EXPORT reclaims animality as a site of resistance, the gesture remains ambivalent: it risks reinscribing the very binary that aligns women with nature and men with culture, even as it attempts to subvert it in very white European way.

From an animal-studies perspective, perhaps animality in EXPORT's work remains in the service of a human-centred project. Animals are not engaged as ethical others, but as conceptual tools through which female subjectivity negotiates shame, repression, and liberation.

In *Wer begreift hat Flügel / Those who understand have wings* (1974), EXPORT works with taxidermied birds, not live animals (Abb. 8). The Centre Pompidou describes the object as a box with six compartments containing six preserved birds, constructed from lead, wood, wax, and paper, and forming part of the *Asemie* ensemble. Rather than presenting animals as symbols of nature or freedom, the work positions them as carriers within a semiotic system.

Each bird occupies a compartment titled *Geschlecht, Semiotik, Nature, Freiheit, Kultur, and Der Preis des Verstehens*¹². Within this configuration, the birds function as material inscriptions embedded in an anagrammatic structure. Meaning is not revealed as essence, nor anchored in the animal body itself, but produced through juxtaposition, categorisation, and displacement.

What is important to say about this work is that the birds lie in named little coffins, almost in the same way people calmly take their assigned places within a conformist system of life. Before the birds were covered in wax, when they were alive, they could fly, move, and be free. Now they are given a beautiful wrapping: elegant letters, loud concepts, impressive phrases.

These phrases are, in themselves, not comfortable, yet they are pleasant to look at. They work visually, they work rhetorically. But if the essence, the movement, and the living impulse behind the concept are dead, then there is only packaging left. Language survives, while life does not.

«Wings» do not signify transcendence in a metaphysical sense, but the capacity to act, to move, and to reconfigure social conditions. Liberation is not achieved by escaping the body,

¹² EXPORT, V. (n.d.). *Werkdetail | VALIE EXPORT*. Retrieved October 3, 2025, from https://www.valieexport.at/jart/prj3/valie_export_web/main.jart?rel=de&reserve-mode=active&content-id=1526555820281&tt_news_id=2223

but by insisting on it as a locus of knowledge, history, and resistance. To «have wings» is thus not to rise above material conditions, but to gain the ability to intervene within them.

Animality is not what is shown here. It is what is lost. What remains is only the body without movement, life without impulse and wings without flight. Animality is classified and archived.

Seen this way, the birds are not «nature» in any naive or romantic sense. They are situated within a conceptual grid that binds biological life to systems of language, culture, knowledge, and power. The object thus extends EXPORT's broader critique of representation by exposing how concepts such as nature, freedom, and understanding are mediated rather than given. It is precisely this logic, the refusal of immediacy in favour of mediated perception, that reappears in EXPORT's filmic and performative works, where bodies and animals are not shown to reveal truth, but to expose the systems in which they are captured.

But at the same time, one can also see something else here: a persistent urge to express human needs through the image of an animal with wings (angelic, winged animal, transcendence imagery). An almost compulsive gesture. As if the human constantly needs another figure in order to speak about itself. The winged animal becomes a convenient metaphor, this animal is no longer fully an animal. It is purified, elevated, symbolised. It is meant to stand for freedom, salvation, transcendence.

In this sense, wings cease to be a possibility of movement and become a sign of compensation. The animal dissolves – and the system stays intact.

2.2 Restriction as Feminist Method

Animal Art did not appear out of nowhere. As Lisa Moravec reconstructs, it emerged from a conflict: the protests by animal rights activists during *steirischer herbst '85* (1985), when site-specific performances involving real animals made ethical tensions impossible to ignore (Moravec, 2023). What was at stake was not only the use of animals, but the limits of avant-garde artistic freedom itself.

Richard Kriesche's reply to this rupture was the exhibition *Animal Art* at *steirischer herbst '87* (1987). Rather than resolving the conflict, the exhibition institutionalised it. The exhibition used animals as «live matter¹³» and as media of artistic communication, which went against bourgeois ideas of the art object and aesthetic autonomy (Moravec, 2023). Animality became a problem the exhibition refused to stabilise.

Moravec reads *Animal Art* as a space where animality functioned as a lens through which bodily discipline, social regulation, and bio-political control could be examined. Artists such as VALIE EXPORT were placed within a broader field of tension between representation, ethics, and the management of life itself. What mattered was not coherence, but friction.

This text takes a different angle. Rather than following the exhibition as a curatorial or institutional project, I move inside the works themselves. My interest is less in animality as «live matter» than in what happens when animal bodies are translated into systems of signs. In EXPORT's work, animals are classified, framed, archived, and immobilised. Animality becomes readable, and in becoming readable, it loses movement.

And therefore, *Animal Art* matters here, because it creates a bridge to VALIE EXPORT's work. EXPORT was included in the exhibition through a photograph of her performance *Restringierter Code*¹⁴, presented at the Lenbachhaus in Munich in 1979, involving actual dogs and small children (Abb. 9). Already here, animality is not decorative. It enters the scene as a problem.

The way humans have domesticated dogs reflects how men have historically wanted women to behave: tamed, loyal, and controlled. In VALIE EXPORT's work, dogs, like other animals, act as reflections of women's position in society. Equally as animals are marginalized, so too are women. In this cultural framework, women are equated with animals but not people.

¹³ This means the exhibition focused on living beings, not representations alone. Animals were not just images, symbols or metaphors. They were bodies, organisms and processes, sometimes literally present, materially preserved (taxidermy) and mediated through film or sound. Animals were not just subjects of art; they functioned as media themselves.

¹⁴ VALIE EXPORT *Restringierter Code (Restricted Code)* 1979. Video (black and white, sound). Duration: 30:39 min.

In her accompanying statement in the dog section of the catalogue, EXPORT describes the body as a means of expression, but a restricted one. A «restricted code». What she points to is sharp: the supposed difference between animal behaviour and human behaviour, between animal bodily expression and human bodily expression, is not natural at all. It is an ideological axiom. A tool of social control. EXPORT and Ingeborg Strobl¹⁵, for example, stand close here, even where they disagree ethically. One works with animals to expose control; the other refuses their use to expose violence.

This tension leads back to EXPORT's birds. What begins in *Restringierter Code* as a restricted body becomes, in *Wer begreift hat Flügel*, a restricted animal. The dogs move. The birds no longer do. They are classified, named, boxed, archived. The «restricted code» hardens into structure. Animality does not disappear, it is immobilised.

Seen from this angle, the birds in their coffins are not an exception, but a consequence. *Animal Art* does not resolve the problem of animality; it exposes how life is captured. EXPORT takes this logic one step further, showing what remains when movement is replaced by legibility, and when understanding finally comes at its price.

Through fatal rituals with animals, EXPORT reveals how deeply humans are entangled in ritual, in the kitchen as much as in the church. These rituals are leftovers; they are lived structures. People do not simply perform them; they are shaped by them. Animal ritual pictures human ritual and shows how little distance there is between them. Animals do not decorate art; they force it into conflict with its own limits.

«HAUT-DIALOG»¹⁶ (Skin-Dialogue) was a 2024 performance by VALIE EXPORT at the Arcaded Courtyard of the University of Vienna. EXPORT placed her arm and hand around the snake that coils around the Castalia statue atop the fountain in the centre of the courtyard. In ancient Greek mythology, Castalia was a nymph from Delphi, pursued by Apollo, who threw herself into a spring to escape him. The snake traditionally signifies fertility, renewal, and transformation through the shedding of skin.

The snake is not animated, yet it is not symbolic either. It functions as an interface. In this sense, *HAUT-DIALOG* extends EXPORT's early *Body Configurations* into a late practice

¹⁵ Ingeborg Strobl (1949–2017) was an Austrian feminist artist closely associated with the postwar Austrian neo-avant-garde and with the circle around steirischer herbst. Strobl's importance in Animal Art lies in her explicit refusal to use live animals, paired with a sharp critique of how animals are already instrumentalised in society. Her photographs, such as those showing lambs at a cattle market or a single goat, do not aestheticise animals; they expose their status as commodities, trained bodies for labour and food chain.

¹⁶ EXPORT, V. (n.d.). *SKIN-DIALOGUE* [Online object catalogue record]. Kontakt Collection. Retrieved October 3, 2025, from <https://www.kontakt-collection.org/objects/6764/skindialogue?ctx=01d7ccf5991ab817650872ac68b61e4859536be4&idx=36>

where animality is no longer staged through movement or sacrifice, but through sustained contact (Abb. 10). What is crucial in *HAUT-DIALOG* is that the animal is not alive, not even seen as sign of nature. It is a sculptural animal, already translated into culture. Animality persists precisely where life has been removed. This is where *HAUT-DIALOG* resonates strongly with VALIE EXPORT's concept of *Asemie* – the refusal of expressive meaning strongly. To the same degree as *Asemie* names the breakdown of facial expression as a stable carrier of sense, the snake here marks a form of animality emptied of vitality but not of presence. In this sense, *HAUT-DIALOG* can be read as a late, distilled version of EXPORT's engagement with animality.

There is a close connection here between the way animals function as a means of deconstructing human power and bodily control in EXPORT's work, and artistic practices that treat animals not as objects, but as participants. This connection can be read as a key parallel. In both cases, the viewer is confronted with the collapse of the familiar role of the observer-as-owner.

In EXPORT's work, the viewer realises that their gaze is not neutral, it is part of a system of violence. In *Animal Art*, as discussed by Moravec, the viewer becomes aware that the seemingly innocent image of «the animal as picture» already belongs to a regime of anthropocentric exploitation. What is exposed in both cases is the same structure (Moravec, 2023).

In both contexts, the body – female or animal – is not decoration. It is political territory. And in both cases, the task is to shift the centre of power: away from the one who controls the image, and toward the body or subject itself, which begins to dictate the conditions of visibility.

The expectations society places on human (female) and animal bodies, the regulation of movement, and the restriction of bodily gestures operate as a form of social control.

Conclusion

From the very beginning, VALIE EXPORT positioned herself at a distance from the spectacular choreography of coercion that defined much of Viennese Actionism. While she moved within the same artistic environment and was briefly associated with Actionist circles, her practice followed a different system. EXPORT refused the escalation of shock through bodily destruction and rejected the use of violence as an end in itself. Instead, she turned to mediation, language, ritual, and socially circulating images as sites where power is produced and maintained. Her work does not seek rupture through excess, but exposure through precision.

This distinction becomes especially clear in relation to animals and oppression. Where Actionism instrumentalised animal bodies as ceremonial material, subjecting them to real harm in order to provoke confrontation, EXPORT displaced force from the level of physical abuse to that of symbolic mechanism. Animals in her work do not absorb acts of harm; they signify it. They function as figures through which obedience, domestication, and hierarchy are made legible. Here, then, EXPORT does not deny violence, but refuses to reproduce it. She foregrounds how hegemonic force operates across gender and species without enacting cruelty, identifying violence as a system rather than an event.

Her feminist position is therefore inseparable from this methodological choice. By rejecting orchestrated brutality, EXPORT insists on the situated body, human or animal, not as a site of sacrifice, but as a site of meaning. Violence is no longer something to be performed on bodies, but something to be read within the social codes that shape them. This shift marks a decisive break from Actionism and situates EXPORT's practice as a critical reconfiguration of confrontation itself.

Actionist violence was not metaphorical. It was enacted. Animals were killed, disembowelled, and displayed, their bodies transformed into instruments for producing affect as disgust, horror, and catharsis. The abuse directed toward animals was justified as a necessity: a means of breaking repression, confronting Austria's postwar moral hypocrisy, or exposing the latent brutality of bourgeois order. Yet this justification unmasking a deeper problem. The animal becomes a substitute victim, a corporeal form onto which acts of mutilation can be displaced without resistance or consequence. In this sense, Actionist animal sacrifice reproduces the very hierarchies it claims to dismantle: domination masked as liberation, control imposed as revolt. The contrast is decisive. Actionism's abuse of animals operates within a

logic of bodies offering and an economy of violation: one body must be violated so that meaning can emerge.

Some sources and online accounts ascribe animal injury to VALIE EXPORT's work. However, in the authoritative literature, including *VALIE EXPORT: In Her Own Words* (Museum Ludwig/Thaddaeus Ropac, 2023) and scholarship such as Widrich (2014), there is no documented performance in which EXPORT kills a bird or any animal.

EXPORT understood the danger of spectacular violence and restructured the dispute itself. The environment she emerged from (Viennese Actionism) *did include animal sacrifice*, but EXPORT's work decisively rejected that framework, choosing interaction and agency over destructive acts and domination.

Although EXPORT never engaged in the literal slaughter used by some Viennese Actionists, she sometimes put on display the *appearance* of violence as a symbolic gesture. A good example is her video *Asemie - The Inability to Express Oneself Through Facial Expression / Asemie – die Unfähigkeit, sich durch Mienenspiel ausdrücken zu können* (1973), in which she seems to kill a small bird, not a real animal, but a constructed object, a sign. The gesture operates on the level of representation rather than brutality. EXPORT brings into view the cultural script of sacrificed bodies, but refuses to provide a real victim. The «bird» becomes a metaphor for fragility, for the historical vulnerability projected onto female bodies, and for the shock-driven brutality circulated in media images. In this way, EXPORT appropriates the vocabulary of extremity but empties it of male-coded cruelty, transforming it into feminist semiotic critique, redirecting confrontation away from mythic spectacle.

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Appendices

Abb. 1: VALIE EXPORT (Austrian, b. 1940)
TAPP und TASTKINO (TAP and TOUCH CINEMA) 1968. Albertina, Wien – The ESSL Collection © VALIE EXPORT, 2022, ProLitteris, Zurich, photo: Werner Schulz.

Abb. 2: VALIE EXPORT (Austrian, b. 1940)
Portfolio of Doggedness (VALIE EXPORT, own words, conversation with Elisabeth Lebovici), in cooperation with Peter Weibel. 1968. Courtesy Galerie Thaddaeus Ropac and the artist © VALIE EXPORT, 2022, ProLitteris, Zurich. Photo: Joseph Tandler.

Abb. 2: VALIE EXPORT/Peter Weibel.

Aus der Mappe der Hundigkeit, 1968. © Sammlung Generali Foundation - Dauerleihgabe am Museum der Moderne Salzburg © Bildrecht, Foto: Josef Tandler

Abb. 3: Installation view *VALIE EXPORT – The Photographs*, Fotomuseum Winterthur
© Fotomuseum Winterthur / Conradin Frei

Abb.3: VALIE EXPORT, *I (Beat It) II*, 1980. Installation / video installation. Three monitors, video tapes, photograph of a woman (VALIE EXPORT) with lead bands around wrists and ankles, lead bands, waste oil. © VALIE EXPORT / Bildrecht Wien.

Abb. 3: VALIE EXPORT, *I (BEAT (IT))*, 1978. Installation / video installation. *Motto*: « Das Leben ist in unseren Händen, auch wenn wir gleiten und uns schwer darin bewegen, aber schlagen wir nicht dagegen, so werden wir verschwinden». Photographs: Dietmar Kirves (Berlin), Robert Fleck. © VALIE EXPORT / Bildrecht Wien.

Abb. 4: VALIE EXPORT, *ASEMIE – die Unfähigkeit sich durch Mienenspiel ausdrücken zu können*, 1973. Video / experimental film. © VALIE EXPORT / Bildrecht Wien.

Abb. 4: VALIE EXPORT (Austrian, b. 1940)

ASEMIE – The Inability to Express Oneself Through Facial Expression 1973. Courtesy Galerie Thaddaeus Ropac and the artist © VALIE EXPORT, 2022, ProLitteris, Zurich Photo: Alfred Damm.

Abb.5: VALIE EXPORT (Austrian, b. 1940)

Action Pants: Genital Panic 1969. Courtesy Galerie Thaddaeus Ropac and the artist
© VALIE EXPORT, 2022, ProLitteris, Zurich. Photo: Peter Hassmann

Abb. 5: Marina Abramovi performing VALIE EXPORT's *Action Pants: Genital Panic*, (1969), *Seven Easy Pieces*, Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum, New York, 2005. Photograph by Attilio Maranzano. Courtesy of Marina Abramovi Archives

Abb. 6: EXPORT, V. (Director). (1976). Still from *Unsichtbare Gegner (Invisible Adversaries)*. [Motion picture]. VALIE EXPORT Produktion. Premiered at the Internationales Forum des Jungen Films, Berlin International Film Festival, 1977.

Abb. 7: EXPORT, V. (1973/2003). *Mann & Frau & Animal* [Experimental film; 16 mm, black-and-white and color; DVD transfer]. VALIE EXPORT Produktion. First exhibited at *The Austrian Exhibition*, Demarco Gallery, Edinburgh.

Abb. 8: VALIE EXPORT, *Wer begreift hat Flügel*, 1974. Object installation with six compartments and taxidermy birds. Lead, wood, wax, paper. © VALIE EXPORT / Bildrecht Wien. Courtesy Centre Pompidou, Paris.

Abb. 9: VALIE EXPORT, *Restringierter Code*, 1979. Performance / video performance with dogs and children.
© VALIE EXPORT / Bildrecht Wien. Courtesy VALIE EXPORT Archive

Abb. 10: VALIE EXPORT, *HAUT-DIALOG / SKIN-DIALOG*, 2024. Performance, Arcaded Courtyard (Arkadenhof), University of Vienna. Black-and-white photographic documentation (5 photographs, 21 × 31.5 cm). © VALIE EXPORT / Bildrecht Wien. Courtesy Kontakt Collection.